

Narrative construction of “AI” through anthropomorphising language in German public discourse

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1. Introduction

This paper investigates how narratives about so-called “AI” (artificial intelligence) as a human actor are constructed in German public discourse and how they change over time and across media. For example, expressions such as *AI colleague*, *AI learns*, or pronominal references such as *‘The AI learns quickly. It adapts to users’ needs.’* construct AI as a quasi-human discourse participant. We define narratives as recurring lexico-grammatical patterns used to anthropomorphise AI in large text corpora and address the following research questions:

- RQ1: Which linguistic units are used for the narrative construction of AI as a human-like actor?
- RQ2: How do anthropomorphic narratives differ between quality newspapers, web texts, and IT blogs?
- RQ3: How do these narratives change after the release of ChatGPT?

Rather than topic modelling or sentiment analysis (Nguyen and Hekman, 2022; Chen et al., 2025; Winkel, 2024), we draw on linguistic studies of anthropomorphism, mainly based on English data (de Haan, 2025; Salles et al., 2020). Specifically, we analyse AI narratives through: 1) anthropomorphic lexemes (DeVrio et al., 2025; Lind, 2025), such as *AI colleague*, 2) pronominal reference to AI (*AI is fast, but it will not replace humans*) as an indicator of AI personification (Abercrombie et al., 2021, 2023), and 3) the syntactic role of AI as subject versus object (*AI is used* vs. *AI uses*).

Following a similar study of English data (de Haan 2025, 20–32), we hypothesise that anthropomorphic lexical units occur more frequently in web texts than in quality newspapers and IT blogs (H1) and become more prevalent after ChatGPT’s release (H2). We also expect pronominal reference to AI in the subject role to be more common in web texts than in newspapers (H3). We further expect pronominal reference in the object role to increase over time (H4).

2. Dataset and methodology

The search string *KI* (German abbreviation for AI) was used to sample 48,965 sentences (41,357 after deduplication) containing the word *KI* from the DWDS corpus¹. We limited our search to quality newspapers, IT blogs, and general internet texts, covering the years 2019–2024. A detailed overview of corpus composition, including the newspaper outlets and yearly frequencies before and after deduplication, is provided in the supplementary materials.² We treat November 30, 2022, the public release date of ChatGPT, as the boundary between the pre- and post-ChatGPT periods. The term becomes more frequent after ChatGPT’s release: 17,019 occurrences of *KI* in 2019–2021 compared to 24,338 in 2022–2024.

Period	Newspapers	IT blogs	Web texts	Total
2019–2021	3,281	6,503	7,235	17,019
2022–2024	12,550	6,976	4,812	24,338
Total	15,831	13,479	12,047	41,357

Table 1: Deduplicated *KI* occurrences by period and medium

After preprocessing in Python (deduplication, metadata splitting, sentence segmentation), we combine NLP methods with manual annotation to trace the linguistic indicators of anthropomorphising narratives mentioned above. To compare media and periods, we normalise all counts by the number of *KI* tokens per medium and period, reporting rates per 1,000 *KI* occurrences.

3. Results

First, we use spaCy’s POS tagging to extract adjectives, nouns, and verbs as the three most common word classes (excluding punctuation, prepositions, and determinatives) in our dataset that immediately precede or follow *KI*. Two annotators classify these neighbours (15,392 sentences) as either non-anthropomorphic or as belonging to one of four anthropomorphic categories: constructing *KI* as an agent (*KI works*), a cognizer (*KI learns*), a communicator (*KI writes*), or a biological metaphor (*KI sees*), following Inie et al. (2024) and the annotation guidelines. Inter-annotator agreement is high ($\kappa = .96$ for the fine-grained categories; $\kappa = .83$ for the binary distinction anthropomorphic vs. non-anthropomorphic). The most frequent anthropomorphising units include the verbs *lernen* ‘learn’ and *schreiben* ‘write’, the adjective *stark* in *starke KI* ‘strong AI’, and the noun *Kollege* ‘colleague’. Web texts show the highest rate of anthropomorphic lexemes only for 2019–2021, but after 2022, the pattern reverses in favour

¹ <https://www.dwds.de/>

² <https://osf.io/8yzt7/overview>

of quality newspapers. Therefore, the hypothesis that anthropomorphic lexical units occur more frequently in web texts than in quality newspapers and IT blogs (H1) is only partially confirmed. Likewise, the hypothesis that anthropomorphic lexical units become more prevalent after ChatGPT's release (H2) is not consistently supported across media.

Across all sources and both periods, agency remains the most frequent category. While IT blogs and web texts show a slight decline in agentive units, newspapers more than triple their use of this category in 2022–2024. Cognizer and communicator categories become more prominent, especially in newspapers and IT blogs. Biological metaphors remain rare but increase notably in newspapers.

Agency is by far the most frequent category ($n = 1,676$), followed by cognizer ($n = 276$), communicator ($n = 129$), and biological metaphor ($n = 83$). The same ranking remains stable over time: in 2019–2021, we find 780 agency cases, compared with 104 cognizer, 14 communicator, and 44 biological metaphor cases. In 2022–2024, agency rises further to 896 cases, while cognizer and communicator increase to 172 and 115 respectively, whereas biological metaphor remains rare (39 cases).

This temporal shift is statistically significant overall: the distribution of anthropomorphic categories differs between 2019–2021 and 2022–2024 ($\chi^2 = 69.09$, $df = 3$, $p < .001$). The same is true within each source type, including newspapers ($\chi^2 = 14.00$, $df = 3$, $p = .003$), IT blogs ($\chi^2 = 46.76$, $df = 3$, $p < .001$), and web texts ($\chi^2 = 25.02$, $df = 3$, $p < .001$). In the aggregate, agency remains the dominant category in both periods, but cognizer and especially communicator labels become more prominent after 2022.

To address H3 and H4, we first analyse how often KI appears as a grammatical subject or object. The subject position with agentive predicates (*AI acts*) marks AI as an agent, whereas the object position (*AI is used*) construes it as a tool or patient (Kako 2006; Primus 2012). Using spaCy's German dependency parser (`de_core_news_md`), we automatically assign roles and validate them on 1,500 double-annotated instances, achieving substantial agreement with humans (Cohen's $\kappa = .71$). Across all years and sources, KI is much more frequently used as subject (a quarter to a third of all occurrences) than as object (fewer than ten per cent), with slightly higher subject shares in newspapers than in other sources. This preference remains stable over time, with only modest increases after 2022.

Next, we retrieve pronominal references to KI using spaCy's Coreferee (Hudson n.d.). Because its evaluation on a stratified, double-annotated subset of 101 cases shows only moderate agreement with humans ($\kappa \approx .54$, $accuracy = .77$), we treat it as a candidate generator and manually verify all positive cases ($\kappa \approx .98$). Overall, pronominal reference to KI is rare but increases slightly after 2022: in 2019–2021, only about 2–2.7% of all KI mentions are followed by human-confirmed pronoun coreference, compared to approximately 2.8–3.5% in 2022–2024. Newspapers show both the highest proportions and the strongest growth over time, with feminine reference clearly dominating over other forms.

H3 (pronominal reference to AI in the subject role is more common in web texts than in newspapers) is not supported: Contrary to our hypothesis, we do not find higher rates of pronominal reference to AI in the subject position in web texts. Normalised rates are higher in newspapers (about 5% of subject-only KI tokens, $\chi^2 = 160.5$, $p < .001$), while web counts are extremely low and sensitive to how AI's syntactic role is parsed. H4 (pronominal reference in the object role increases over time) is supported: the probability of pronominal reference to KI in object position increases significantly from 0.17% to 1.49% between 2019–2021 and 2022–2024 ($\chi^2 = 12.1$, $p = .0005$).

4. Conclusions

The analysis shows that German public discourse produces “distantly read” narratives of AI that shape expectations about its agency (e.g., *AI doctor*), cognitive (e.g., *intelligent AI*) and communicative capabilities (e.g., *AI says*). In general, combining NLP methods with human annotation enables digital humanities scholars to trace large-scale patterns in narratives about emerging technologies.

The dataset construction, annotation, and analyses are complete. Ongoing work focuses on further keywords, such as ChatGPT, possessive constructions (e.g., *OpenAI's KI*), sentiment analysis, and topic modelling.

References

Abercrombie, Gavin, Amanda Cercas Curry, Mugdha Pandya, and Verena Rieser. 2021. Alexa, Google, Siri: What are Your Pronouns? Gender and Anthropomorphism in the Design and Perception of Conversational Assistants. In Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Gender Bias in Natural Language Processing, pages 24–33, Online. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2021.gebnlp-1.4>

Abercrombie, Gavin, Amanda Cercas Curry, Tanvi Dinkar, Verena Rieser, and Zeerak Talat. 2023. Mirages. On Anthropomorphism in Dialogue Systems. In Proceedings of the 2023 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, pages 4776–4790, Singapore. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2023.emnlp-main.290>

Chen, Mo, Ian Cody Koratsky, Fanjue Liu, and Seungahn Nah. 2025. Generative AI in the News: The Impact of Framing on Public Attitude and Engagement. In Artificial Intelligence in HCI: 6th International Conference, AI-HCI 2025, Held as Part of the 27th HCI International Conference, HCII 2025, Gothenburg, Sweden, June 22–27, 2025, Proceedings, Part III. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, 3–21. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-93418-6_1

De Haan, Tjerk. 2025. Tracing the Humanisation of AI: A Computational Analysis of Agentic Language in News Media and Twitter Discourse on ChatGPT. Master's Thesis. Utrecht University. <https://studenttheses.uu.nl/handle/20.500.12932/50042>

DeVrio, Alicia, Myra Cheng, Lisa Egede, Alexandra Olteanu, and Su Lin Blodgett. 2025. A Taxonomy of Linguistic Expressions That Contribute To Anthropomorphism of Language Technologies. In Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '25). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 430, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3706598.3714038>

Hudson, R. P. n.d. Coreferee. spaCy. Coreference resolution for English, French, German and Polish, optimised for limited training data and easily extensible for further languages. GitHub. <https://github.com/richardpaulhudson/coreferee>. Retrieved October 22, 2025.

Inie, Nanna, Stefania Druga, Peter Zukerman, and Emily M. Bender. 2024. From “AI” to Probabilistic Automation: How Does Anthropomorphisation of Technical Systems Descriptions Influence Trust?. In The 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '24), June 03–06, 2024, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 26 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3630106.3659040>

Kako, Edward. 2006. Thematic role properties of subjects and objects. *Cognition*, 101(1), 1-42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2005.08.002>

Lind, Miriam. 2025. Alexa’s agency: a corpus-based study on the linguistic attribution of humanlikeness to voice user interfaces. *AI & Society* 40, 4619–4633. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-025-02243-8>

Nguyen, Dennis, Erik Hekman. 2022. The news framing of artificial intelligence: a critical exploration of how media discourses make sense of automation. *AI & Society* 39, 2, 437–451. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-022-01511-1>

Primus, Beatrice. 2012. *Semantische Rollen*. Winter. https://www.winter-verlag.de/es/detail/978-3-8253-5977-5/Primus_Semantische_Rollen/. Retrieved October 22, 2025.

Salles, Arleen, Kathinka Evers, and Michele Farisco. 2020. Anthropomorphism in AI. *AJOB Neuroscience* 11 (2): 88–95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21507740.2020.1740350>

Winkel, Marek. 2024. Controlling the uncontrollable: the public discourse on artificial intelligence between the positions of social and technological determinism. *AI & Society*, 40, 3, 1947–1959. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-024-01979-z>